

**PITCH-BASED HIGH MODULUS CARBONFIBER FOR
CONSTRUCTING LARGE IRRIGATION WATERWAY TROUGHS**

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ABSTRACT

This paper concerns development of irrigation waterways of a large CF-hybrid FRP construction to be installed on the soft soil. Hybrid structure incorporating pitch-based high-modulus carbonfiber : [FORCA-FT500] was chosen to build troughs having necessary rigidity with economic cost performance.

Keywords : Irrigation waterway, CF-hybrid FRP, Pitch-based high modulus carbonfiber

1. INTRODUCTION

Reported below is the process of development of irrigation waterways made of composite materials and constructed on a soft soil. The Ishikari river in Hokkaido, located in the most northern part of Japan, runs in a soft soil including a peat bed 30meters deep. The area along the river provide local farmers with paddy field for growing rice. To get enough water from the river to the rice paddy, bearing piles that are long enough to reach a technically stable ground under the soft soil at intervals of several meters apart, and concrete or steel irrigation troughs are built upon them. These structures are so heavy that a large number of piles are needed a given distance. This for many years presented a need for a long span trough, at least 2 meters wide and having sufficient durability to carry the water, for forming an economical, light weight, strong and rigid trunk waterway for irrigation.

The author of this paper and his associates are credited for earlier having developed a 75 meter water pipe trough made of CF-hybrid FRP to be attached to an existing bridge structure^{1) 2)}, as well as flood-gates for waterway made of similar hybrid FRP³⁾.

Based on this proven development and the results of organized researches by the technical committee of The Japan Reinforced Plastics Society⁴⁾, a new project was initiated in search of possibility to replace the heavy, conventional irrigation structure with a room for further improvement, was accomplished using pitch based high modulus carbonfiber that contributed to successfully increasing the structural rigidity as detail below.

2. BASIC CONSIDERRATION

The initial attempt of the project was to substitute the conventional concrete trough with a CFRP structure having the same section (2m wide and 0.8m deep) and rigidity.

All the load conditions that the new trough could be subject to were analyzed carefully. Figure 1 shows one of shape that was acquired from a basic structural analysis.

A series of these basic studies led to a possibility of building the desired long-span trough by the use of CF-hybrid material mainly consisting of GFRP.

Figure 1. A basic structural analysis

3. DESIGNING : USING A PICH-BASED HIGH MODULUS CARBON-FIBER

The length of a trough was set at 12 meters segment each on the result of structural analysis and the legal restriction for carrying the prefabricated troughs to the site on a trailer truck. A goal was set then to design a trough that, when installed, would withstand a pile-to-pile distance of 12 meters maximum. The resulting irrigation waterway was to bear a maximum load of 16.32 tons.

The surface creating a waterway was to be formed by GFRP while the side walls were to be stiffened by light gauge rectangular steel pipe and fabricated in a truss structure. The bottom was given a sandwich structure having a balsa core. The bottom was also to be integrated with a reinforcement frame so that the resulting waterway would stay by itself between two piles like a bridge rather than relying on bearing capacity of the soil underneath.

The bottom stiffened frame was to be construct by rectangular pipes assembled in a grid-like design and made of unidirectional CF-hybrid GFRP acquired by pultrusion. The bottom frame must be lightweight as well as highly rigid. For the reason of efficiency, the project group including author naturally chose a pitch-based high modulus (500GPa) carbonfiber : [FORCA-FT500] (Tonen Corp.) as the hybrid material because of its unusually high performances. Table 1 shows properties of the UD-CF hybrid GFRP rectangular pipe used as the bottom stiffened component. It demonstrates a substantial weight reduction the steel counterpart of the same rigidity. Figure 2 shows the whole figure of waterway trough. Figure 3 shows its cross section and Figure 4 shows its construction.

The trough itself would weigh 2.29 tons and its total load would be 18.61 tons when filled with water to the full capacities. The load along its length would be borne by a truss structure integrated with the composites reinforcement at the bottom of the side walls. Figure 5 shows analytical pattern and the results of its vertical displacement.

The maximum sag over 12 meter span was calculated to be only 10.66mm, sufficiently less than the targeted ratio of 1/300, due to combined effects of light weight CF-hybrid FRP longitudinal reinforcement.

The moment, shear stress and axial stress were also calculated of the upper and bottom members, longitudinal members and diagonal members of the truss at the side walls to determine stresses acting on it in varying temperatures.

Table 1. Properties of CF-hybrid GFRP pipe

<p>Pipe Section</p>	Material Properties	
	MODULUS	GFRP : 26 GPa CFRP : 200 GPa
	E I	GFRP : $2.67 \times 10^2 \text{ KN} \cdot \text{m}^2$ GFRP+CFRP : $7.31 \times 10^2 \text{ KN} \cdot \text{m}^2$
<p>The hybridization increases flexural modulus of GFRP by around 2.7 times. This corresponds to the modulus of a rectangular steel pipe 125×125×3.2mm in dimension while reducing the weight to only about 22% per given length. This apparently allows substantial improvement in terms of weight.</p>		

Figure 2. Whole figure of Waterway Trough

The FRP panels at the side walls and the bottom were also subjected to stress analysis to predict the trough's dry stage under wind pressure when installed as a waterway bridge. Safety factors were finalized respectively according to the analytical results.

Figure 3. Cross section of Waterway Trough

Figure 4. Construction of Waterway Trough

Figure 5. Analytical pattern of vertical displacement

4. MAKING AND INSTALLATION

The troughs were made using male wood mold and GFRP was molding by the hand-lay-up method with glassmat and roving cloth. The stiffeners was overlaid to integrate the assembly.

The troughs were transported on a trailer from the factory to the site of installation, where they were unloaded by a crane onto the brackets on bearing piles that had been driven 12 meters apart. The adjacent troughs were bolted together via rubber sheet packing at flanges provided on the ends of each trough. Because of the light weight, the entire installation work was unbelievably easier and faster compared to the conventional methods. Photo 1 shows the hoisting work. Photo 2 shows the installed waterway. Photo 3 shows the waterway in use.

Photo 1. Hoisting work of installation

Photo 2. Installed Waterway

Photo 3. Waterway in use

5. TESTING AND EVALUATION

The waterway was tested carefully through the year to evaluate its dynamic behavior and structural characteristics in use.

A total of 34 measuring points were selected over the 12 meter span. Strain gauges and displacement meters were used to measure the occurring stress and the deflection respectively.

The temperature in the part of Hokkaido where the waterway was installed goes down to -20°C with the snowfall of 1.2 meters in winter. The temperature rises to as high as 30°C in summer.

The waterway is used for irrigation for approximately three months from May to early August.

To summarize the results of strain measurement, the amount of displacement resulting from sagging due to the water weight during the irrigation season was 9 millimeters. This value was in proximity of the initial calculation. Stresses occurring at the measuring points generally coincided with the predicted values during analysis.

However, a close examination of the behavior of the measured values suggested presence of stress most likely resulting from thermal expansion due to the rise in temperature. This indicates that the waterway is generally under a greater strain when it is empty due to the ambient temperature than to the water when it is in use.

6. CONCLUSION

In comparison with the conventional material for building waterways, the new waterway trough reported herein proved a number of characteristic and functional improvements.

Furthermore, it promised a greater ease as well as higher accuracy of installation while requiring hardly any maintenance.

The hybrid effects of pitch-based high-modulus carbonfiber, especially contributed substantially to increasing the structural rigidity of the GFRP structure that normally lack rigidity. This waterway trough uses steel material for an economical reason. Its weight represents 42% of the trough's dry weight. Further reduction of weight and gain of rigidity is achievable by replacing the steel parts with the CF-hybrid GFRP. This presents a fair possibility of developing wider and deeper troughs that will mark even more favorable cost performance.

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AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

